

The Wavefunction As a Self-Measurement Function

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 30, 2023

In a previous note (1), we called a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ a self-measurement function in that it physically represents a kind of dynamical (two dimensional) spatial probability and entropy associated with the dynamical information p , i.e. momentum.

In this note, we wish to examine this idea in more detail by considering Lagrangian theory, but not for a free particle, but for a Bohm Aharonov situation. The derivative of the Lagrangian dL/dv partial yields a value for canonical momentum, but v , velocity, follows from an external, not internal, measurement. On the other hand, momentum assumes motion in x and so a function of x could be considered a self-measurement function if it were dynamic, i.e. did not depend on external measurements in the usual sense of Newtonian dynamics. In order to convert the Lagrangian theory into one linked with a spatial derivative (which is a generator of translations), one may create the action i.e. $\int L dt$. Thus, we suggest that one move from an external measurement picture given by Lagrangian theory (and Newtonian mechanics), to an internal measurement one given by the action. The action, however, becomes a linear function in x for a constant p and this then depends on an external origin and measurement, whereas creating a periodic eigenfunction does not. Its physical attribute is the wavelength in space which is an internal measurement which may interact with external objects with such a spatial frequency (so to speak) such as two slit interference apparatus with slit separations of \hbar/p .

Newtonian and Lagrangian Mechanics

Newtonian and Lagrangian mechanics are based on external measurements which do not disturb a moving particle. The question we asked in (1) is whether one could have an internal physical built-in self measurement mechanism instead. We suggested that a free particle quantum wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ is just this.

Here we wish to consider this self-measurement function in terms of its relationship to Lagrangian mechanics. From Newtonian mechanics, it is known that momentum is proportional to a physical impulse. Momentum follows mathematically through the use of a derivative (i.e. generator) from:

$$dL/dv \text{ partial} = p \text{ canonical } ((1)) \quad \text{where } L \text{ is the Lagrangian}$$

V , velocity, however, is obtained from external measurements, i.e. one has to measure the particle move a dx in a time dt , and so a clock is needed as well. We ask: Is there a way to convert an external measurement picture into an internal one? This begs the question: What would an internal measurement picture be like? We suggest that the information p could manifest itself through a physical property, say resolution, in another dimension, say space. In such a case, one would have to convert the velocity derivative in ((1)) into a spatial one. This may be done through the use of the classical Action = $\int L dt$.

For a constant p particle in the absence of a magnetic potential, it is known that the action (relativistic or nonrelativistic) may be written as:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

where $E = \gamma m_0 c^2$ and $p = \gamma m_0 v$ relativistically and $E = p^2/2m_0$, $p = mv$ nonrelativistically. Here $v = x/t$.

We have investigated ((2)) in earlier notes. Here we wish to focus on the more complicated situation of coupling with a magnetic vector potential $A_{\text{vec}}(x,t)$. Even in such a case, ((1)) holds and so the notion of seeking an action function which yields momentum through d/dx partial is still valid.

The Lagrangian for a charged particle in the presence of magnetic vector potential and electrostatic potential V is given in (2) by:

$$L = mv^2/2 + q/c \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{A}(\text{vec}) - qV \quad ((3))$$

$$\mathbf{P} = dL/d\mathbf{v} \text{ partial} = mv + q/c \mathbf{A}(\text{vec}) \quad ((4))$$

Mathematically, one may create a classical Action = Integral $L dt$ and then obtain an expression for p canonical by using a d/dx partial instead of d/dv partial.

$$\text{In such a case: Action} = p x + \text{Integral} (0,x) q/c \mathbf{A}(\text{vec}(x')) dx' \quad ((5)) \text{ for } p=\text{constant}$$

One may argue that both Lagrangian theory and Action theory are simplifying mathematical approaches which yield the results of Newtonian mechanics, which is based on external measurements which do not disturb a dynamic system. This is true, but does not stop one from speculating that there may be a physical self-measurement mechanism built-into dynamics. The first hint of this comes from Fermat's least time principle, where minimization with respect to time becomes mathematically equivalent to taking a d/dx (and not d/dt) derivative, which in turn equates conserved x momentum components before and after refraction of light.

We suggest that momentum is directly related to dynamics and motion in space. Thus, there could possibly be a physical mechanism linked to changes in x which yields information about p . We suggest that the action given in ((5)) is an important first step, but given that it is linear in x , it still depends on an external measurement based on an origin. To bypass this and make the function a self-measurement or self-information one, one may create an eigenfunction, namely:

$$\exp(i \text{Action}) \quad ((6))$$

This then exists in all of space, but is periodic if one only has a constant p and no A_{vec} . For the case of A_{vec} (magnetic vector potential), matters become more complicated, but d/dx , the translational generator, still yields the momentum at x . Thus, we argue that ((6)) (which is a

wavefunction in quantum mechanics) is an information or self-measurement function which does not require external measurement.

To see explicitly that this represents an internal measurement scheme, one may consider the case of $\exp(ipx)$, no A_{vec} , and note that such a particle interacts with a 2-slit system if the slits are about \hbar/p apart. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ carries internal information about p incorporated in terms of spatial frequency. This is apart from the fact that p renders an impulse hit proportional to its value. In the case of a constant p and an A_{vec} not linked with any B field which changes the particle, A_{vec} leads to a phase shift which may also be measured. Thus, $\exp(iAction)$ really does appear to be an internal dynamic information function.

As a result, we suggest that derivatives really constitute measurements because they are equivalent to translational generators which in turn describe infinitesimal physical changes. We thus try to base the creation of self-measurement function on the eigenfunction of a possible internal variable such as x . Given that Lagrangian theory already contains a measurement in terms of d/dv we suggest converting L to a function which yields the same p result upon taking d/dx partial.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have suggested in (1) that a quantum free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ is really a built-in self-measurement or information function about p momentum. A physical spatial frequency (i.e. wavelength) manifests the value of p . This, in turn, is linked to d/dx partial, the generator for spatial translations as we suggest that momentum implies dynamics and motion in x . Dynamics are not so simple as considering d/dx , but as a start we consider Lagrangian theory in which $p = dL/dv$ partial. In other words, the Lagrangian is an information function, which when acted upon by d/dv partial, yields information p . V , velocity, however, is an externally measured function and we wish to have an internal one like x . Thus we convert L into classical action through $\int dt L$. This leads to $p = dAction/dx$ partial.

We consider the case of a charged particle moving in a magnetic vector potential A_{vec} and electrostatic potential V to go beyond the picture of a constant p particle in free space. Given that one wishes to have an internal function, Action is not sufficient. One may say that for a constant p , px is part of the action, but it depends on an external measurement from a given origin. This is not a self-measurement. Furthermore, Action is a real function and does not seem to capture dynamical internal motion. We suggest using $\exp(i Action)$. This contains two dimensions associated with motion in one direction (i.e. either to the left or right). We suggest that this breaks from usual static probability, but that is fine, we wish to have a dynamical quantity which physically encodes the value of momentum, through the wavelength \hbar/p . The value of p may be obtained without an impulse measurement, by using a two slit apparatus such that slits are separated by about \hbar/p . This is the way to decode the wavelength which is a physical self-measurement value of p . Thus, we suggest that Lagrangian theory, used to recreate the results of Newtonian mechanics, which is based on external non-disturbing measurements, may be converted into an internal measurement theory by using the classical action.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Resolution Entropy? (preprint, zenodo, 2023)
2. Wachter, Simon. The Aharonov Bohm Effect (ETH Zurich 2018)
https://ethz.ch/content/dam/ethz/special-interest/phys/theoretical-physics/itp-dam/documents/gaberdier/proseminar_fs2018/06_Wachter.pdf